
BRAIN DRAIN AND BRAIN GAIN SYNDROME (An Empirical Examination of Push and Pull Factors)

By

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Abstract

The study examined the relationship between brain drain and brain gain syndrome (push and pull factors). The push and pull factors include economic factors, social and political factors, professional factors, environmental factors, personal factors, educational factors, government and policy factors, technology, and infrastructure factors. A cross-sectional research design was used for the study. The population of the study is 16 public universities. The entire 16 public universities were adopted as sample size under the census sampling method. Being a macro study, five lecturers from each university were used as respondents for the study; a total of 75 respondents were used for data collection. The geographical scope of the study is the South East Region of Nigeria. The content scope is the relationship between brain drain and brain gain syndrome. The unit of analysis is organizational. The questionnaire used for data collection was designed in Linkerts format. Descriptive statistical tools were employed for data analysis for demographic and univariate data, while inferential tool of Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient was applied for bivariate and multivariate analysis. Findings show (1) that most push and pull factors are recurring decimal as both brain drain and brain gain factors. (2) That insecurity and threat to life are the strongest push factors for brain drain.(3) That unemployment and poor working conditions are highly rated as strong push factor for emigration. (4) That persistent brain drain from a particular country, if not checked and controlled, can lead to a failed state. The study concluded that push factors are results of the inability of the government to create an enabling environment for professionals, skilled people to be gainfully employed, and semi-skilled and unskilled citizens to be meaningfully engaged in productive activities. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the government should identify elements of push factors and initiate policies to address them.

Key words: Unemployment and under employment, security threat, poor work condition, prejudice in hiring, brain drain and brain gain, greater credential recognition.

Introduction

Numerous opportunities and challenges have been brought about by social networks, globalisation, and the explosion of knowledge occasioned by the internet. A faster flow of people, trade, investment, and knowledge, as well as the mobility of skilled individuals, have also been the outcomes. Many national officials see the forces of globalisation as a threat, whereas others see them as an opportunity (Bhagwati, 2011). In this era of postmodernism, multiculturalism, and aspirational cosmopolitanism, new economies are emerging, and there are numerous issues linked to global migration (Golding et al., 2012). Given that international migration is a worldwide issue, the impact on countries varies, while developed countries gain significantly from immigrants into their country (brain gain), while developing countries lose vital human capital; that is, they are drained of the best of their best brains (Gupte and Jadhav, 2014). The rise of globalised economies is one major reason why societies are losing some of their most brilliant members to other nations. In the context of policymakers, globalisation represents a threat to developing nations but an opportunity for developed economies.

People have been forced to work abroad due to prolonged uncertainty of the future, persistent insecurity, an unfavourable social, political, and cultural environment persistently prevailing in their home country, and the weakness and incompetency on the part of government to provide adequate solutions to prevailing negative situations. Those factors leave the citizens who have the opportunity with no choice but to escape by looking for greener pastures outside the shores of their country, and they act according to the dictates of prevailing circumstances in their home country. Numerous talented individuals are fed up with the prevailing political crisis, insecurity, economic hardship, failed judiciary system, etc. currently ravaging some countries where governments are even found guilty of not respecting the law and judicial pronouncements. Think of a situation where corruption is almost being institutionalised, gaining ascendancy by receiving indirect endorsement among the people in authority. This is a situation where national common wealth is not used for common good but is selfishly and wrongfully appropriated by public authorities and politicians to themselves, and the generality of the citizens are impoverished. The ineptness and cluelessness of the government in addressing these issues makes the situation look more worrisome and hopeless; consequently, a talented, skilled, and unskilled labour force are compelled to migrate for safety and seek alternative sources of income to sustain immediate and extended family members (Goldin et al., 2012).

The present study provides a platform to empirically validate the strengths and weaknesses of some push and pull factors of brain drain and brain gain. That is, which of the push factors is more adoring in motivating migration abroad (Jakpaa in our modern local parlance). The consequent movement of professionals and skilled and unskilled human capital from one country to another is termed brain drain. According to Syerko (2015), brain drain is the aftereffect of the exodus of highly educated people from a nation, including professionals, scientists, and intellectuals, to other countries. Since the advent of globalisation, spatial mobility has been a significant feature impacting national and global economies. Brain drain highlights the consequences of transferring highly educated people from developing to developed countries. It refers to the international transfer of human resources. Brain drain is a global phenomenon that depicts the worldwide migration of resources in the form of human capital from one nation to another.

In literature and in local Nigerian jargon, the term Jakpaa (emigration) refers to the movement of highly qualified professionals with university training, such as scientists, engineers, academic and medical doctors, and other health workers, who leave their own country permanently to live and work in another country. This situation is long recognised as a major barrier to the growth of developing nations. The brain drain is also a source of concern for several African nations, including Nigeria, as well as other third-world countries, where a sizable portion of their skilled labor force has recently left and many more are still leaving for other countries.

According to the Phillips Consulting report (2023), over 52% of Nigerian professionals strongly desire leaving their jobs in Nigeria and moving abroad. To further support this observation, The Nigeria Human Resources Director Network asserts in their 2024 annual general meeting that the professions most likely to lose their employees to the Jakpaa syndrome are in the areas of health care, finance and insurance, professional services, education, and information technology. Up to 90% of the workers in these industries are considering leaving Nigeria for Europe and other countries for permanent residence (ILO, 2023).

The Nigerian economy faced a number of difficulties that contributed to the high rate of brain drain, including underemployment, unemployment, a weak currency, ongoing insecurity that threatened citizens' lives, and the government's incapacity and unwillingness to take decisive action to address the problem. According to the research, the situation has made the high cost of living even more severe and impacted the workers' budgets and purchasing power. On the other hand, it was said that the two most important challenges of the day are preventing brain drain and retaining employees. Furthermore, workers' finances and productivity at work are being impacted by the growing cost of living (WTO, 2021).

As a result, workers are increasingly concentrating on increasing their income streams, stabilizing the economy, and raising their standard of living. Many are moving overseas, obtaining better paying for their professional services, or starting a "side hustle" in order to accomplish these goals. As a result, the attrition rate in important areas has significantly increased. The causes of this increasing brain drain are well known: on the supply side, the globalisation of the global economy has reinforced the propensity for human capital to concentrate in areas where it is already plentiful and increased the likelihood that migrants will choose to remain in their home countries. Furthermore, because of their increasing implementation of quality-selective immigration restrictions, host countries are presently engaged in what seems to be a global competition to entice top talent (This Day News Paper, 2024).

Western countries facing demographic ageing are attracting professionals from third-world countries to fill available positions via attractive policies and advantageous infrastructure. In order to reverse the trend and address the prevalence of brain drain or jakpaa syndrome, third-world governments must create and put into effect a set of policies that will produce a balance of push and pull forces. For example, Nigeria is seeing an increase in the number of citizens leaving the country for other countries, particularly those who are skilled but dissatisfied with the sociopolitical and economic climate there. It seems that there are no specific government initiatives to stop or reverse brain drain. While social order, political stability, economic prosperity, community peace, and property and life protection are all good government goals, brain drain will spread like wildfire across Nigeria. It is against this

backdrop that it becomes imperative to categorically weigh the push factors against the pull factor, especially as it affects universities in southeast Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the study

The study aimed at determining the impact of the push and pulls factors on brain drain and brain gain on universities in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives are to determine

1. If underemployment influences brain drain or brain gain among universities academic staffs in the South East Nigeria
2. To determine if security threats are a brain drain or brains gain among universities academic staffs in the South East Nigeria.
3. The correlation between poor working conditions and brain drains among universities academic staffs in South East
4. To determine if prejudice in hiring and advancement influence brain drain or gain among universities academic staffs in South East
5. To determine if need for greater credentials and recognition influences brain drain or brain gain among universities academic staffs in South East.

Research Questions

The following study questions are derived from the preceding particular objectives.

1. How does underemployment influence brain drain and gain among universities academic staffs in South East Nigeria
2. Is, security threats a brain drain or brain gain factor among universities academic staffs in the South East Nigeria.
3. What is correlation between poor working conditions and brain drain or brain gain among universities academic staffs in South East
4. Is prejudice in hiring and advancement a determinant of brain drain or brain gain among universities academic staffs in South East
5. How does need for greater credentials recognition on brain drain or brain gain among universities staffs in South East

Significant of the Study

The importance of this study lies in the fact it will help to espouse the causes and remedies of high migration in the South East, especially among university lecturers. Moreover, a better understanding of the consequences of the wrong reason for migration will help reduce the Jakpaa syndromes currently invoked in many parts of former eastern and western Nigeria. The study will help the government and their agents to effectively identify and tackle the causes of the Jakpaa syndrome in Nigeria. Finally, the outcome will serve as research material for future researchers on the causes and implications of brain drain and brain gain in the Southeast and beyond.

Scope of the Study

The study is limited in content to brain drain and brain gain (a two-edged sword).

The study is limited unit to public universities in south East. Finally, it is limited in geographical scope to Public Universities in South East Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Brain Drain

According to the United Nations (2023), the term "brain drain" refers to the global movement of human capital resources. It is described as the migration of highly educated people from underdeveloped to developed countries. However, in colloquial use, the phrase is often used more narrowly to denote the movement of highly educated professionals, such as doctors, engineers, and scientists, who regularly move around wealthy nations. The Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English defines brain drain as the exodus of highly skilled and seasoned academics from their own nation to one where they may earn a higher salary. According to Utile (2008), the phrase "brain drain" refers to the widespread exodus of highly skilled workers from one nation to another in pursuit of greater income. From the perspective of the university system, this phenomenon is seen. It can also refer to countries where people move in search of better opportunities, ranging from better employment conditions to better living conditions in other countries. According to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2010), the term "brain drain" initially referred to the movement of technology professionals from one nation, industry, or field to another, usually in pursuit of better job prospects and/or living circumstances. The opposite of brain drain is brain gain, which occurs when trained personnel migrate to developing countries. Both events are viewed as financial costs for the countries that release the migrants because the migrants usually take with them a portion of the value of their training that was funded by the government or other organisations.

The term "brain drain" was first used to describe the exodus of technological workers from a country; today it also refers to the movement of professionals and educated individuals from one country, economic sector, or field to another, typically in search of better employment prospects and/or living conditions. The brain drain has long been seen as a major obstacle to the growth of developing nations, even while it affects wealthy nations. According to comparative statistics, the member countries of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) housed 20 million highly qualified immigrants by the year 2000. Higher-educated foreign-born workers are referred to as these immigrants. This suggests a 70% increase in only ten years. Of these highly skilled immigrants, two-thirds were from developing and transitional nations.

Brain drain-attracting factors.

The components that lure professionals away from their home nation and towards another are referred to as pull factors. These strong pull variables fall into several groups, which are as follows:

(1) Economic pull factors include competitive pay and benefits, improved employment possibilities, chances for career development and promotion, grants and financing for research, opportunities for entrepreneurship, tax breaks and rebates, and a low cost of living. Professional pull factors include things like having access to cutting-edge technology, modern infrastructure, a creative and collaborative work environment, chances for professional growth and advancement, recognition and reputation on a global scale, networking opportunities and conference access, and a diverse and inclusive work culture.

(2) Social and cultural pull factors, including linguistic and cultural linkages, cultural variety and tolerance, access to healthcare and education, family-friendly environments, quality of life and work-life balance, social security and stability, and recreational and leisure activities.

(3) Personal draw elements include the assurance of one's own safety and security, the climate and topography, the availability of outdoor recreation and nature, the choice of an urban or rural lifestyle, and the closeness of family and friends, freedom of religion and spirituality, a feeling of belonging and togetherness. Academic reputation and credentials, research opportunities, language and training programs, financial aid and scholarships, the international student community, access to top-ranked universities, online courses, reliable internet access, data supply, and other intellectual resources are some of the educational pull factors.

(4) Government and policy pull factors, such as favourable visa policies, expedited immigration procedures, tax breaks and rebates for professionals, government-funded research projects, assistance for new businesses and entrepreneurs, an innovation-friendly regulatory environment, and international collaboration and agreement.

(5) Environmental pull factors include things like access to natural resources, clean air and water, urban planning and green areas, legislation protecting the environment, and eco-friendly infrastructure.

(6) Infrastructure and technology pull factors, such as access to cutting edge transport systems, high-speed internet and connectivity, cutting edge data centres and cloud services, cutting edge urban planning, digital infrastructure, cyber security, and research parks innovation hubs.

Western countries facing demographic ageing are attracting professionals from third-world countries to fill available positions through attractive policies and favourable infrastructure. In order to reverse the trend and address the incidence of brain drain or jakpaa syndrome, third-world governments must create and put into effect a set of policies that will produce a balance of push and pull factors. For example, Nigeria is seeing an increase in the number of citizens leaving the country for other countries, particularly those who are skilled but dissatisfied with the sociopolitical and economic climate there. It appears that there are no specific government initiatives to stop or reverse brain drain. While social order, political stability, economic prosperity, communal peace, and property and life protection are all goals of good governance, brain drain will spread like wildfire through Nigeria. Against this backdrop, it becomes absolutely necessary to balance the pull and push elements, particularly as they relate to South East Nigerian universities.

The push factors of brain drain.

The push factors refer to negative circumstances or situations that drive or push professionals and skilled workers away from their home country to live permanently in another country where they consider it favourable and conducive to living. These push factors can be classified into five categories as indicated hereunder.

(1) **The economic push factors** such as low salaries and poor benefits, limited job opportunities, unemployment and underemployment, economic instability or recession, high taxes and costly living, limited career advancement opportunities, poor working conditions,

(2) Social and political pull factors such as political instability and persistent life-threatening conflicts, corruption and unnecessary bureaucratic measures, lack of freedom and human rights, social inequality/discrimination, limited access to education and health care, poor infrastructure, high crime rates, and persistent insecurity and safety concerns.

(3) Professional pull factors, which include limited research funding/opportunities, obsolete technology/equipment, and lack of opportunities for professional development, advancement and training, poor work-life balance, unfavourable work environment/culture, limited opportunities for entrepreneurship

(4) Environmental push factors such as climate change/natural disaster, pollution / environmental degradation, limited access to natural resources, overcrowding/urbanisation, and poor air or water quality.

(5) Personal push factors, which include factors like family/marital issues, health concerns / medical needs, personal safety / security concerns, limited access to cultural recreational activities, and desire for new experiences.

Push factor of brain drain factor—The Nigerian experience.

It is an important and worrying topic as to why Nigerian intellectuals and professionals have left the country, or whether they are considering it at all. Many of Nigeria's most intelligent people are leaving the nation for other parts of the globe, especially the West, for a variety of reasons. According to studies, one of the main reasons for the flight of intellectuals and professionals from Nigeria is the harsh economic conditions that they face. Secondly, they want to visit countries where they may use their competitive advantages (Adebayo, 2010). Social, political, and psychological factors also contribute to Nigeria's brain drain, as they push intellectuals and professionals outside in search of more favourable conditions for their personal and professional lives. Consequently, it should not be shocking when people seize opportunities to benefit from better opportunities in other countries when they present themselves. A summary of the push factors is provided below.

Effect of Brain drain on Nigeria

(1) Significant Decline in the Caliber of Skilled Labour in Nigeria's Research Centers, Teaching Hospitals and Tertiary Institutions

The issue of diminishing educational levels in Nigeria is related to the decline in the number of trained workers in the nation's higher education institutions. *Ipsa facto*, a large number of seasoned intellectuals are leaving these institutions—particularly the ivory tower—in large numbers to pursue better chances abroad or in other economic sectors of the country. Therefore, it should come as no surprise that there will be a major reduction in both the quantity and calibre of academic staff. Viewed from this angle, Mbanefo (2020) correctly observed that "the Nigeria university system is still beset by intellectual haemorrhage caused by the brain drain problem today." This is particularly true, he claims, in the crucial fields of human medicine, pharmacy, computer science, and engineering. In a similar vein, Adebayo (2010) reports that in the 1990s, a great deal of higher education institutions (HEIs) in Nigeria were made into hollow shells and superficial institutions, and many hospital and research facilities in the country lacked specialists and consultants. This scenario makes it abundantly evident that the flow of technology know-how cannot support a thriving economy.

(2) A Sharp Drop in Academic Standards

There is little question that the quality of the work produced by Nigeria's higher institutions has suffered from the large-scale departure of highly skilled and experienced academics in search of better prospects overseas, particularly from its universities. As correctly pointed out by Yesufu (1996), the calibre of graduates is so low that their productivity impact on the national economy is typically lower than what is necessary for a developing economy. Two ways that the brain drain impedes economic progress are the depletion of a source country's human capital assets and unpaid educational investments. When skilled professionals from wealthy nations were being attracted to developing nations in the late 1960s, the phrase gained widespread usage. It is a highly relevant issue once more because skilled migration flows have increased dramatically, partly as a result of overt poaching practices. Because of the brain drain, receiving countries are seeing an increase in demand, and their immigration laws reflect how welcoming and dependent they are on skilled immigrants.

Two ways that the brain drain impedes economic progress are the depletion of a source country's human capital assets and unpaid educational investments. When highly skilled professionals from wealthy nations were attracted to such countries in the late 1960s, the phrase gained widespread usage. It is now a very relevant issue because skilled migration flows have increased dramatically, partly as a result of overt poaching practices. The brain drain is creating a pull in demand for the receiving countries, and these countries' immigration policies mirror the shortages in their own labour markets. When paired with traditional supply-side self-selection effects, the outcome is significant large rates of migration among the highly educated and greater transfers of human capital from developing countries (Beine et al., 2001).

The Viewpoint of Gender on Brain Gain/Drain

According to Docquier et al. (2014), while taking into account the majority of the OECD between 1990 and 2000, the rate of growth of highly skilled women is slightly higher than that of low-skilled women and highly-skilled men. Skilled women also show a larger tendency to move than their male counterparts. There was a tender gap (in favour of men) in total emigration rates, despite the fact that high-skill female migration was expanding at a higher rate in 2000 due to the fact that they are more frequently targeted in labour migration, particularly in the domestic and caregiving sectors. Ten years later, the evidence no longer supported this conclusion; in 2010 and 2015, the opposite could be proven. However, less developed countries are losing their human capital. As a result, over time, there has been an increase in studies on how female skilled emigration affects the economy, labour market, education, and welfare of women left behind. But compared to the rate of migration in Nigeria, women in the 1980s and early 1990s were more likely to migrate, particularly to nations like Italy, France, and the UK. From the late 1990s to the new Millennium, there was an abrupt reversal in the trend, with males overtaking women in the workforce. As a result of the new trend, more males were moving to Australia, South America, and Europe (Agrawal et al 2011).

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the change theory or (push-pull) by Lewin (1947)

The study of behavioural intention—which arises from competing sensations of pleasure and frustration in social settings—was the aim of the change theory. Lewin's theory states that two things affect a situation: forces, also known as push factors, and assisting factors, also known as pull factors, which direct and accelerate movement in the direction of a goal. People's willingness to participate, according to Miller (1967), is based on how much their wants and the perceived comfort or suffering in the social context that shapes decision-making align or diverge. The idea provided an explanation of the "push" and "pull" mechanisms that lead individuals to migrate from their native country, or "source," to different places with different cultures. The policy study uses the terms "pull" and "push," which relate to the carrot and stick (Enderwick et al., 2011). Pull factors—new behaviour or reality—also serve as justification for decisions to shift, according to Lewin's 1947 original theory, but push forces typically serve as the foundation and fundamental grounds that explain the urge to change. As a result, a country seeking to halt brain outflow may consider developing a plan that supports and concentrates on the push factors that lead to brain drain. When presented with challenges, people form opinions, which triggers the pull factor to make them react and alter their behaviour (Baruch, 1995). In a similar vein, Kim et al. (2011) found that professionals are compelled to travel abroad due to push factors in their immediate surroundings that influence decision-making.

About the brain drain and push-pull paradigm that Lam and Hsu (2006) discussed, the split of a person's choice of travel location into two components is the fundamental idea of the push and pull model. They contend that the first force is the push factor that exists in the person's native country, which exerts internal pressure and affects their inclination to join the movement. The second part is the draw factor, which has an impact on an individual's attitude because of how beautiful they believe the destination to be. Thus, these factors affected people's opinions, behavioural intentions, and choice to relocate in pursuit of a better life.

Empirical Review

Plethora of studies has been conducted among which include:

Syerko (2005) evaluated students' ambitions to pursue higher education abroad at 13 constituent institutes of the University of Zagreb. The sample used numbered 553 respondents, and the rationales why they studied abroad were classed as push and pull factors. According to the study findings, students identified the most crucial push factors that made them to depart their country.

Golub's (2003) study on the professional and social situations of young researchers found that 63.3% of those under 35 were considering working abroad. Survey respondents cited low salaries, unresolved housing issues, and a low standard of living as reasons for moving abroad. They also cited better conditions for scientific work and creativity, as well as a negative perception of science and scientists in society.

Mlikota and PrelasKovacevic (2013) investigated the motivations of University of Virovitica students to go abroad. The survey of 196 respondents found that the top reasons for leaving the country were financial reasons (15%), better living conditions (14%), job opportunities (13%), and a better future (11%). Only 5% of respondents expressed conservative views and dissatisfaction with the country's leadership. The majority of students (18%) said that their family, parents, and girlfriends or boyfriends were the most significant reasons for staying in

their home country, while 17% cited friends and social connections as the most important. The students picked the United States, Canada, Australia, and Germany as their favourite travel destinations.

Kizito et al. (2015) studied the intentions of recent medical students to leave Uganda, as well as the factors influencing these intentions. The study was conducted between 2012 and 2013. A total of 251 medical students participated in the study. The following factors were ranked in order of importance as factors that influence students' decision to stay in Uganda after graduation: lack of government (41.7%), lengthy emigration processes (36%), high living expenses in the foreign country (33.1%), lack of family support (29.5%), racism in the foreign country (27.3%), satisfaction with the circumstances. Despite Uganda's need for health workers, the study found that many respondents planned to leave their jobs or go outside the country.

Kaliyati (2009) investigated what factors influence a person's decision to stay or leave New Zealand. The factors were classified into two categories: economic considerations and non-economic factors. The most significant component was the perception of New Zealand's employment policy, with findings indicating that men are more affected by this feature than women. Student loan debt was the second most significant cause.

Kazlauskienė and Reinkevicius (2006) studied the factors influencing the relocation of highly educated Lithuanian labour force to identify the source of the country's brain fuga. The Wilcoxon test, based on a sample of 416 highly educated Lithuanians who had previously lived abroad, found that attraction factors had a significant impact on the tendency of brain fuga.

Docquier and Rapoport (2012) investigated the topic of brain emigration and the factors that influence the decision to relocate abroad. The study focused on three cases of brain emigration: doctors in Africa, scientists in Europe, and technology workers in India. European scientists cited a lack of funding for science in their own countries as the primary reason for leaving.

Efendic (2016) investigated the emigration intentions of Bosnian and Herzegovina residents, whose backgrounds and environments are comparable to those of Croats. The results show that among the respondents, they are young, educated, and have little income.

Efendić (2016) investigated the emigration intentions of Bosnian and Herzegovina residents with comparable backgrounds and environments to Croats. Their findings indicate that respondents who are young, educated, and have a low income are more likely to want to immigrate.

Ette and Witte (2021) investigated the economic and non-economic drivers of migration in Germany. According to the data, people planning to leave their home country for a foreign country prioritise financial benefits, employment opportunities, social capital, mobility capital, and job satisfaction.

Ndiangui (2021) conducted research on the factors that influence the migration of university graduates. The study found that most university graduates left their home country not only because it was difficult to find affordable and competitive jobs, but also because they were unaware of the existence of such jobs and travelled abroad in search of them.

Khan (2021) examined a collection of qualitative studies from 2000 to 2020 to identify the causes of academic brain drain in Europe. There were identified five critical elements: (1) Competitive pay outside of Europe; (2) Fixed-term contracts for academics at the start of their careers; (3) Discriminatory hiring practices; (4) Attractive immigration policies; and (5) The indirect contribution of internationalisation policies to promoting permanent mobility.

Summary of Literature and Gap in Literature

The Jakpaa syndrome is not unique to Nigeria, but its negative effects and incalculable losses affect Nigeria more than other African countries (Federación de Migración Humana y Lucha contra la Trata de Personas, 2022). This is shown by the fact that 6 out of every 10 people that die in the Mediterranean Sea are Nigerian (FHMAT, 2023). This implies that more Nigerians, directly or indirectly, are attempting to migrate outside of Nigeria. Dr. Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala, the Director General of the World Trade Organisation, has stated that the Jakpaa rate in Nigeria is alarming. She has urged the Nigerian government to create an environment conducive to resolving the Jakpaa incident, which has cast the country in a negative light. Several studies have been conducted on the effects of cross-border migration, with various reasons given. However, the consequences are clear in all cases: brain loss and gain from one country to another. However, no study has specifically examined the cost and benefits of migration, focusing on universities in southern Nigeria. This study filled a gap by analysing each of the four expulsion and attraction factors used in the study, which included public universities in the south.

Research Methodology

The study adopted correlational research design to examine the relationship of some push factors in motivating brain drain among university lecturers in the South East Nigeria. The choice of correlation design lies in the fact that it will enable us to observe natural relationships between the push factors and migration in South-East. The population for the present study are drawn from among university lecturer in all the public universities (made up of federal and state universities in South-East Nigeria. A total of 15 public universities in South-East Nigeria. Table 3. 1 shows the distribution of the public universities among the five states in South East. Public universities are universities owned by either federal government or state.

Fig 3.1 showing the distribution of public university among the 5 states in South-East

State	Federal Universities	State Universities
Abia State	1	1
Anambra	1	1
Ebonyi	1	1
Imo	1	6
Enugu	1	1
Total	5	10

Source: Emmanuel Mogaji, 2019

Table 3.1 above shows that there fifteen (15) public universities in the South east Nigeria. To ensure adequate representation this study we choose five participants from each of the public universities. The participants are made up Head of Departments (HOD), Professors, associate Professors, Senior Lecturers, and assistant Lecturers. The respondents are selected from five faculties where the universities suffer severe brain drain, namely faculty of medicine and health sciences, faculty of Engineering, faculty of management sciences, faculty of science

and faculty of social sciences. Table 3.2 shows the total population of participants in the study

Table 3.2 showing the population of respondents selected from five faculties

S/N	Faculty	Number of participants
1	Engineering	5
2	Social sciences	7
3	Science	10
4	Management science	10
5	Medicine	25
	Total	57

Order of selection was based on observed trend, in many cases of migration or Japa as widely reported by some media (Daily Trust, 2023, the Economist, 2023) secondly, there is no denial to the fact that medicine is far more than a faculty in university, but a school considering the number of departments in the school of medicine. It is important to note that the study adopted census sampling technique. Also, the study relied on the use of primary data, sourced through the use of structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed in a five likert formant.

4.1 Data presentation, Analysis, discussion of finding

A total of 57 questionnaires were distributed via WHATSAPP and physical distribution to participants. 42 or 74% of the questionnaires were successfully retrieved, while 5 or 26% questionnaire were rejected based on there were not properly filled and inappropriate for the analysis.

Table 4.1 showing how the respondents responded to the questions on underemployment (N=42)

S/N	Push-Factor (underemployment)	SA	A	MA	DA	SDA	Mean	Std
1	I have always served in the capacity of part time staff/assistant from the inception of my employment	23 (55%)	10 (23%)	0 (0%)	4 (10%)	5 (12%)	4.00	0.605
2	As a part-time staff I have limited opportunity for career growth.	22 (52%)	13 (31%)	1 (2%)	5 (12%)	1 (2%)	4.19	0.645
3	Am still hunting for better employment	24 (57%)	15 (36%)	1 (2%)	2 (5%)	0 (0%)	4.45	0.707

Source: The result of SPSS descriptive analysis.

The preceding Table 4.1 shows how respondents responded to the underemployment questions. The item aims to assess the ease with which professionals may get full-time employment by asking "Have you always worked as a part-time personal/assistant since starting your job?" The 23 percent, or 55%, of those polled agree that they had worked as an assistant and on a part-time basis. The 10 or 23% just agree, while the 0 or 0% are somewhat agreeable. The four, or 10%, are in disagreement, while the fifteen, or 12%, are strongly disagreeing. The survey results show that most respondents agree that finding full-time work

and advancing to a higher level is challenging. This implies that they are not fully employed, as seen by a high average value of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.605. The second item aims to assess job satisfaction as a consequence of part-time employment by asking, "As a part-time employee, I have limited opportunities for professional growth." The responses show that 22 or 52% of those polled are very agreeable, 13 or 31% are just agreeable, and 1 or 2% are somewhat agreeable. While 5 or 12% disagree, 1 or 2% strongly disagree. The survey results show that the majority of respondents are dissatisfied with their jobs, with a mean score of 4.19 and a standard deviation of 0.645. They are looking for new jobs both within and outside of Nigeria. The third point assesses respondents' readiness to accept a new job in any location by asking whether they are still looking for a better job. The response shows that 22 or 52% are very much in agreement, 13 or 31% are simply in agreement, and 1 or 2% are somewhat in agreement. Similarly, 5 or 12% disagree, although 1 or 2% strongly disagree. The average score of 4.19 indicates high agreement, with a standard deviation of 0.645. Once again, the results show that our respondents are quite open to migrating from the southeast region where they now live and travelling abroad or to Jakpaa.

Table 4.2 showing how respondents responded to the question on threat to security (N=42)

Security Threats	SA	A	MA	DA	SDA	Mean	Std
My job hunt is cuts across local and international boundaries and depends on perceived security of my life and that of my immediate family.	24 (57.14%)	15 (35.71%)	1 (2%)	1 (2%)	1 (2%)	4.429	0.702
The fear of attack by bandits is my greatest concern in selecting place of residence and work	20 (47.52%)	18 (42.86%)	0 (0%)	3 (7.14%)	1 (2%)	4.262	0.662
I prefer to reside in country where my life is not under any form of threat.	22 (52.38%)	20 (47.62%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4.524	0.726

Source: SPSS output, 2024

Table 4.2 illustrates the replies of responders to the security threat questions. Item one tries to determine if the security hazard of employment location influences respondents' choice of where they want to work inside and outside of the country by asking whether their job search crosses local and international borders. Their answer indicates that 24 or 57.14% of respondents strongly agree, 15 or 35.71% just agree, and 1 or 2% of respondents partly agree. Similarly, 1 or 2% of respondents disagreed, whereas 1 or 2% strongly agreed. According to the responses, the majority of respondents believe that the safety of life and property is a crucial factor of where to live (in their local surroundings or overseas). This is backed by a large mean value of 4.429 and a standard deviation of 0.702. Item two tries to determine if fear of attack impacts respondents' choice of where to work and live by asking whether the fear of bandit assault is a big worry when deciding where to work and live. The findings suggest that 20 or 47.52% of respondents strongly agree, 18 or 42.86% just agree, and 0 or 0% partly agree. 3 or 7.14% of respondents disagree, with 1 or 2% strongly disagreeing. The findings suggest that safety of life and rate are the most important factors in determining the push factor for migration. This is confirmed by a high average score of 4.262 and a standard deviation of 0.662. Finally, item three emphasised the importance of safety for life and property while determining where to live. The result indicates that 22 or 52.38% of

respondents highly agree, while 20 or 47.62% merely agree. There were no opposing views, meaning that none of the respondents would ever choose to work or live in an unstable environment. As a result, the safety of one's life is a major factor in deciding whether or not to move.

Table 4.3 showing how the respondents responded to the question on the poor working condition (N=42)

S/N	Poor Working Condition	SA	A	MA	DA	SDA	Mean	Std
1	The most important factor I consider before accepting to work in any organization is good pay packet irrespective of country	20 (47.62%)	18 (42.86%)	1 (2%)	3 (7%)	0 (0%)	4.310	0.673
2	Am more attracted to an organization by hygiene factors in an organization	19 (45.24%)	20 (47.62%)	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	2 (5%)	4.262	0.662
3	I prefer the use of such reward factors as: per hour payment, commission, part ownership	21 (50%)	17 (40.48%)	2 (5%)	2 (5%)	0 (0%)	4.357	0.684

Sources: SPSS output 2024

The preceding Table 4.3 shows how respondents responded to the question on working conditions. The first point aims to determine the ranking of compensation factors that motivate or discourage employees from staying or migrating to other organisations within and outside of the country. Employees are asked if "the most important factor that I consider before accepting a job is a good salary independent of the country." The response demonstrates that 20 or 47.62% of the respondents are very much in agreement, 18 or 42.86% are simply in agreement, 1 or 2% are moderately in agreement, 3 or 7% are in disagreement, and 0 or 0% are not. A median score of 4,310 is a strong indicator of agreement among respondents, while a standard deviation of 0,673 indicates that a reward system in particular may serve as an attractive element. In contrast, a low remuneration scale will operate as an expulsion factor, motivating the movement. The second point aims to determine if hygiene is a significant motivator for employees to relocate from one country to another. Employees are asked if they are more drawn to an organisation due to hygiene factors such as work environment, well-being, security, and job security. The results show that 19% (45.24%) of the respondents are very agreeable, 20% (47.62%) are just agreeable, and 0% are somewhat agreeable. Similarly, 1 or 2% of those polled disagree, while 2 or 5% strongly disagree. The findings suggest that hygiene has a significant role in influencing migration decisions among respondents. This is supported by a high average value of 4,262 and a standard deviation of 0.662. As a result, we conclude that the hygiene element is both attractive and repellent. It is a factor of expulsion if the working environment is inadequate, unsafe, and poses a high risk to occupational safety. Countries that provide a positive work environment, job security, and security are more likely to attract professional workers. The third item seeks to determine the most inductive method of compensation preferred by the surveyee by asking: "I like the use of remuneration factors such as hourly pay, commission, and partial ownership of the

organisation." The responses show that 21 or 50% of those polled agree that the shape of the reward system is a major driver, 17 or 40.48% simply agree, and 2 or 5% agree somewhat. Similarly, the 2 or 5% is in both disagreement and agreement, and the 0 or 0% is strongly disagreeing. The implication of the conclusion is that the kind of compensation is a key predictor of whether or not to migrate, and so may be classified as a factor of expulsion if it is insufficient and a factor of attraction if it is considered high. The previously obtained results strongly support the opinion that the type of compensation is a significant determinant of expulsion and attraction. This is supported by an average value of 4,357 and a standard deviation of 0.684.

Table 4.4 below shows how the respondents responded to the question on question is credential an important determinant of migration

S/N	Greater credential recognition	SA	A	MA	DA	SD	Mean	Std
1	Academic qualification is a priority for migration to another country	10 (24)	8 (19)	5 (12)	10 (24)	9 (21)	3	0.244
2	Emphasis should be on ability to carry out the job rather than paper certificate	15 (36)	18 (43)	3 (7)	4 (10)	2 (5)	3.88	0.339
3	I prefer countries that emphasis less on paper qualification and more of practical knowledge.	20 (48)	18 (43)	0 (0)	1 (2)	3 (7)	4.21	0.650

SPSS output, 2024

In Table 4.4, the first question aims to determine if academic qualifications are a priority for international migration or migration from one country to another. The results show that 10%, or 24%, are very much in agreement, 8%, or 19%, are simply in agreement, and 12%, or 5%, are somewhat in agreement. Similarly, 10%, or 24%, are in disagreement, while 9%, or 21%, are strongly disagreeing. The previous result suggests that academic qualification is not a priority for migration from one country to another. The average score is 3 and the standard deviation is 0.244, both low, indicating that academic qualification is not a strong motivator. However, it may serve as an attractive factor for countries that require it. The second goal is to determine the criteria for selecting the desired criteria by the survey, such as whether the ability to do the work should be prioritised above paper qualification. The results show that 15%, or 36%, of the respondents are very agreeable, 18%, or 43%, are just agreeable, and 3%, or 7%, are somewhat agreeable. Similarly, four or ten percent disagree, while two or five percent disagree strongly. The survey results show that the majority of respondents believe that skill, rather than paper qualification, is an attractive feature.

Finally, the third point aims to determine whether respondents prefer countries with a focus on skill rather than paper qualification. The results show that 20% prefer countries that prioritise skill over paper qualification, while 18% prefer countries with a focus on skill. The above conclusion implies that skill is a strong exclusionary factor for migration in contrast, a strong attraction factor.

Discussion of findings

It is observed that most push factors are reoccurring decimal as both brain drain and brain gain factor. These findings are consistent with the theoretical conclusions in previous works carried out by other scholars. For instant, economist like Beine et al., 2001 and 2003, Stark, 2005 assert that countries with abundant human resource should trade on such factor in other

to reduce the incidence of underemployment. Moreover, based on ILO (2021) recommendation that countries where supply of labour exceeds the demand for labour, the country can export excess labour to reduce the incidence of both unemployment and underemployment. At this point, we can boldly say that a country with many years of continuous rise in unemployment and underemployment shows encourage migration of surplus human resource to countries where they are needed, such instance may not be regarded as brain drain since there is no clear brain drain disadvantage incident. Therefore, a country with high labour supply can export the excess to gain income and reduce unemployment.

Another noticeable observation from the result we obtained is that, insecurity is a strong push factor for brain drain, migration in this instance may not be linked to any economic benefit or pull factor. This finding opens up a new area of study, with emphasis to ascertain any correlation between insecurity and brain drain using empirical stance. However, according to Checci et al, (2017), war torn countries experience great migration and brain drain. Those who migrate during insecurity are most young people. Therefore, the finding of this study has empirically affirmed direct relationship between life insecurity and brain drain. This finding also corroborates the work of Katz and Rapoport (2015) the duo assert that human life security is ranked highest among the push factors of migration. By implication if the incident of brain drain must be minimized in institutions in South East Nigeria, government must intensify effort in providing adequate security of life and properties.

The third finding reveals that working condition is highly rated as a strong push factor of migration, virtually previous study affirmed strong relationship between good work condition and brain drain. Countries with poor work condition find it difficult to retain their work force and prevent them from migrating abroad. International labour organization attested to this outcome, according to ILO(2023) many developing nations lose their vital human resource to developed nation, because the latter have better work condition and environment, good reward system and well negotiated job security. Work condition is a push factor to home country and a pull factor to foreign country.

Finally, the argument of academic qualification as a push factor has not gained much attention and debate, although it has been argued that professional men and highly skill worker are more prone to migrate compared to less professional and unskilled workers (Bhargava & Docquier, 2019). However, recent development in some developing countries has shown that number of non-skilled workers migrating to Europe has witness upsurge, instance, according to international migration organization report (2023), Nigeria top the list of country from African countries that migrate to Europe in 2023, with annual growth rate of 12.5%. The number shows that unskilled labour figure was estimated to be 7.3% from 2.4%. According to United Nation report on global migration, global migration can only reduce if countries address those push factors propelling migration, especially in developing African countries.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study has dealt extensively with the issue of push and pull factor as a double edge sword. It is double edge sword because a push factor in one country is a pull factor in another country. The major conclusion to be drawn in this study is that push factors are the result of inability of the government to create enabling environment for professionals to be fully employed in their home country. Government should identify the push factors and initiate policies to address them. However, for those that intend to migrate or Jaka, the cost and benefit of push and pull must be carefully considered or weighed. Based on the above finding the study recommends as follows

- i. Our educational curriculum should be fashioned in such a manner as to make the receiver self-reliant and capable of creating employment not just for him or herself but for at least one person
- ii. Government should tackle the issue of insecurity in the south East through the application of non-kinetic approach (use of dialogue, compensation, amnesty, reconciliation and development of infrastructure) in South East
- iii. Government should evolve better labour policy that takes cognisance of work place environment, hygiene-factors in work place, good reward system that integrate self-actualization of the employees while working.
- iv. Discrimination at work place along ethnicity, gender, race, religion consideration should be avoided, since this factor result into brain pull.
- v. There should be new policies that place lesser priority on paper qualification. Allow the best hand handle the job.

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